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      *           20           *           40           *           60           *           80           *           100
GbTMEM214-1_A : -----MESVDLHETPTN----- : 11
GbTMEM214-1_D : -----MESVDLHETTN----- : 11
GbTMEM214-4_A : -----MDSVDLHVVHETAASNGG : 18
GbTMEM214-4_D : MVHNEQKKNQGCKGNKLLISVSVLGSSGPIRFVNVNEGELVGTVIDIALKSYAREGRYFLDRIILMSFFFIPVLVDMHMRFLITDSVDLHVVHETAASNGG : 100
GbTMEM217-7_A : -----MMDENSAMIEILREFFENEDG : 21
GbTMEM217-7_D : ----- : -
                                     s
      *           120           *           140           *           160           *           180           *           200
GbTMEM214-1_A : ANHVDHCGQKVSYPKQRKTKENADP---NLPRSNGLTLNGSASVFRSLEQQSEDRRRRIVEAQRAYAATAADADAKSKPKRSVITDDSDDDGSDLLGKVK : 108
GbTMEM214-1_D : ANHVDHCGQKVSYPKQRKTKENADP---NLPRENGTLNGSASVFRSLEQQSEDRRRRIVEAQRAYAATAADADAKHKPKRSVITDDSDDDGSDLLGLK : 108
GbTMEM214-4_A : ANHTDHCGQKVSYPKQRKTKSKADPEKEN-TRLSGTLTDGGENVFRSLEQQSEDRRRRILEAQRAYAADVVDADAKVNNRSDLDLDDDD---SDLEGVK : 114
GbTMEM214-4_D : ANHTDHCGQKVSYPKQRKTKSKADPEKENLTRINGTLINGGENVFRSLEQQSEDRRRRILEAQRAYAADVVDADAKVNNRSDLDLDDDD---SDLEGVK : 197
GbTMEM217-7_A : KNDVVNDIKTVSYSKRNRKPSKPLPSG---GFSDLYNGVSSVFSISICKHSEDRRRFAEAFAAKFAAVSSA--VSNQVKVDEDD---SDTGVVE : 112
GbTMEM217-7_D : -----MAASPMSF---ARSRNIRIARVVAQPKLWRRK--QRLVVKVDEDD---SDTGVVE : 50
n   w   vsy   kr   rk           6F   s   s   dRrRi   ea   a   a           a           r   6DD   DD   SD   G6
      *           220           *           240           *           260           *           280           *           300
GbTMEM214-1_A : ENGRKADEEKRAKCKPKPKPVTVFAAAKIDPTDLSAYFAEAWNG---EQQEIQMCKEFADYYGKAFQIVVACQFFWLKLFRESTVAKIADIPLSHISDAV : 205
GbTMEM214-1_D : ENGRKADEEKRAKCKPKPKPVTVFAAAKIDPTDLSAYFAEAWNG---EQQEIQMCKEFADYYGKAFQIVVACQFFWLKLFRESTVAKIADIPLSHISDAV : 205
GbTMEM214-4_A : ENGRKADEVKRVKCKPKPKPVTVFAAAKIDFAFLSVHFAEAWNG---EQQEIQMCKEFANFYGKAFQEVVACQFFWMMFRESTIIRKADIPLSHISDDV : 211
GbTMEM214-4_D : ENGRKADEVKRVKCKPKPKPVTVFAAAKIDFAFLSVHFAEAWNG---GQEQIQMCKEFANFYGKAFQEVVACQFFWMMFRESTIIRKADIPLSHISDDV : 294
GbTMEM217-7_A : ENG--AVEIKRVKCKPKPKPVTVFAAAKIEAGDLSAFIDITSSSYETQDDIQIMRFADYFGRAFASVSAQFFWLRFKESTVSKIVDIPLSNVPEDV : 210
GbTMEM217-7_D : ENG--AVEIKRVKCKPKPKPVTVFAAAKIEAGDLSAFIDITSSSYETQDDIQIMRFADYFGRAFASVNAQFFWLKLFKESTVSKIVDIPLSNVPEDV : 148
NG   A   KK   K   KKKPKPK6TV   EAA   KI           L3   1           QQ   IQ6   4FA155G4AF   V   A   QFFW646F4EST6   KL   DipL5   6   V
      *           320           *           340           *           360           *           380           *           400
GbTMEM214-1_A : YKTSADWISQSRSLFALGFVFIWSLDIILEDDIAAQCASAKGSKKGAQQTSLKSKVGFIFVALAMVLRKPKDALISVLPKLRENSKYQGQDKPEIFVWTVCA : 305
GbTMEM214-1_D : YKTSADWISQSRSLFALGFVFIWSLDIILEDDIAAQCACAKGSKKGAQQTSLKSKVGFIFVALAMVLRKPKDALISVLPKLRENSKYQGQDKPIFAWTVCA : 305
GbTMEM214-4_A : YKTSADWISQCSLFAIGFVFIWSLDIILEDDIVAQCANAKGSKKSVQPPSSKSKVGFIFVALAMVLRKPKDALISVLPKLREGSKYQGQDKLEVIIVMICA : 311
GbTMEM214-4_D : YKTSADWISQCSLFAIGFVFIWSLDIILEDDIVAQCASAKGSKKSVQPPSSKSKVGFIFVALAMVLRKPKDALISVLPKLRENSKYQGQDKLEVIIVMICA : 394
GbTMEM217-7_A : YKTSVDWINRRSLDVIIVSVFIWSLYSICADLASHQCATKSKKVECFALSKSIVAFIVLMSALRRKPKDLVLSLAPKLREDEKYQGQDKPEIIVMICA : 310
GbTMEM217-7_D : YKTSVDWINRRSLDVIIVSVFIWSLYSICADLASHQCATKSKKVECFALSKSIVAFIVLMSALRRKPKDLVLSLAPKLREDEKYQGQDKPEIT-----A : 242
YkTs   DW6   SL   aL   FVIWslD   I   DL   Q   KGSKK   Q   KS   V   IFV   L   M   L   RPKD   LIS6   PKLRE   KYQGQDK   P6   w   i   qA
      *           420           *           440           *           460           *           480           *           500
GbTMEM214-1_A : SKGDLAVGLYIWAHLLLEVLISRKN-CNPQSRDLILQIIVEIILVSKARSIIIVNAVRKGERLIVPESSFEIIMRATFFEASSSRVKATERFEAIYPTVKEVA : 404
GbTMEM214-1_D : SKGDLAVGLYIWAHLLLEVLISRKN-CNPQSRDLILQIIVEIILVSKARSIIIVNAVRKGERLIVPESSFEIIMRATFFEASSSRVKATERFEAIYPTVKEVA : 404
GbTMEM214-4_A : SRGDLAVGLYIWAHLLLPVGGKN-CNPQSRDLILQIIVEIILVSKARTIIIVNAVRKGERLIVPEASFEIIMRVTFEASSSRVKATERFEAIYPTVKEVG : 410
GbTMEM214-4_D : SRGDLAVGLYIWAHLLLPVGGKN-CNPQSRDLILQIIVEIILVSKARTIIIVNAVRKGERLIVPEASFEIIMRVTFEASSSRVKATERFEAIYPTVKEVA : 493
GbTMEM217-7_A : ICGDLAVGLYIWFVLLFEMISDSSSNPQSRDLILQIIVEIILVSKARPIIIVNAVRKGDRLVPESSALLIIMRITFEASSSRVKATERFEAIYPTLKEVA : 410
GbTMEM217-7_D : ICGDLAVGLYIWFVQY-----SAAYAEWQVKLIIISIKARPIIIVNAVRKGDRLVPESSALLIIMRITFEASSSRVKATERFEAIYPTLKEVA : 328
GDIAVGLY   W   h   llp           k   cnpqSrdlilqlVe   I6s   KAR   IIVN   AVRKG   RLVEp           IIMR   TFFA   S   RVKATERFEaiYPT6KEVA
      *           520           *           540           *           560           *           580           *           600
GbTMEM214-1_A : LAGSHGSKAMRCAALCMFAFAIKAAEGSPELSKFAAGTIWICINCAECYKQDVKVYLDNLEASVVLRRISDEWKEHSTKLTTLPLRETIVKFNKN : 504
GbTMEM214-1_D : LAGSHGSKAMRCVALCMFAFAIKAAEGSPELSKFAAGTIWICINCAECYKQDVKVYLDNLEASVVLRRISDEWKEHSTKLTTLPLRETIVKFNKN : 504
GbTMEM214-4_A : LAGSHGSKAMKCVSIOIFHFAKAAAGDGIPELSKFAAGTIWISINCAECYRIIEKAYLDNLEASVVLRRISDEWQHSTKLTTLPLRETIVKFNKN : 510
GbTMEM214-4_D : LAGSHGSKAMKCVSIOIFHFAKAAAGDGIPELSKFAAGTIWISINCAECYRIIEKAYLDNLEASVVLRRISDEWQHSAKLTTLPLRETIVKFNKN : 593
GbTMEM217-7_A : FAGSISG-----IPELSKASDVIWICITQNECYKQDVKVYLDNLEASVVLRRISDEWKEHSTKLTTLPLRETIVKFNKN : 489
GbTMEM217-7_D : LAGSHGSKAMKCAQILSYVKAAGEGPELSKFAAGTIWICITQNECYKQDVKVYLDNLEASVVLRRISDEWKEHSTKLTTLPLRETIVKFNKN : 403
LAGS   GSKam   q   q   a   kaag   PELSKFA   6   IW   L   QN   ECY4   W   YLDNL   AsV   VLR4L   wk   h   k   t   d   lret   k   fr   kn
      *           620           *           640           *           660           *           680           *
GbTMEM214-1_A : EK-MGNESDAATRALFQADKYCKLIAGRLSRCPGCLKSLAFIVVAFVCAAVVAENDDWENKLYVVI-----SSQIEV----- : 579
GbTMEM214-1_D : EKEMGNESDAATCALFQADKYCKLIAGRLSRCPGCLKSLAFIVVAFVCAAVVAENDDWENKLYVVI-----SSQIEV----- : 580
GbTMEM214-4_A : EKAMSNADAVRQSLFQADKYCKHISGKLSRCHGCLKALAFIVVAFVCAAVVTENIDPSDWSKLSAIGTADWNKLSALSTADWNKLSKVFSS : 606
GbTMEM214-4_D : EKAMSNADAVRQSLFQADKYCKHISGKLSRCHGCLKALAFIVVAFVCAAVVTENIDPSDWSKLSAIGTADWNKLSALSTADWNKLSKVFSS : 689
GbTMEM217-7_A : KKAELIAD----ASLKFADKYCKLIAGHFSNCHGCLK-----IFTLDQSEAFGINFTTIGPHL----- : 545
GbTMEM217-7_D : ----- : -
k           adkyc           g   s   g   gclk           g           n

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Figure S2. The amino acid sequence alignment of GbTMEM214s. The alignment was performed with MEGA 5 software and visualized with GeneDoc software.